

Toposequence Study of Soils along Donga River in Manya, Takum Local Government Area Taraba State, Northeast Nigeria.

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Abstract

A toposequence soils study was undertaken along Donga River in Manya, Takum LGA Northeast Nigeria. Three (3) profile pits were sunk using physiographic positions (upper slope, mid-slope and valley bottom) and the soil samples were collected based on genetic horizon differentiation, the samples were subjected to routine laboratory analysis. Data generated was analyzed statistically using coefficient of variance and weighted mean. All profile pits were geo-referenced using hand held GPS receiver. Soil colour ranged from dark brown (7.5YR 3/2) in the Ap horizons to strong brown (7.5YR 5/8) in the Bt horizons. Sand and silt dominated the fractions (sand mean content 43.00 g/kg⁻¹, 71.47 g/kg⁻¹ and 39.64 for Pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively and silt mean at Bt2 had 558 g/kg⁻¹, 366 g/kg⁻¹ and 680 g/kg⁻¹ for Pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively). The bulk density was higher in the top soils than in the sub soils, the highest mean was recorded in pedon 3 (1.57 g/cm³). The silt clay ratio (SCR) was indicative of soils with weatherable minerals. The soil pH ranged from moderately acid to slightly acid (6.48, 5.80, 5.95) in pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The negative Δ pH values obtained are indicative that the colloidal fraction had exchangeable capacity. The total nitrogen was rated low while available phosphorus was rated very high to high. The percentage base saturation had mean from 96.72%, 97.12% and 95.79% in pedons 1,2 and 3 respectively, suggestive of Alfisols -Entisols mix. There were varied results for coefficient of variation (CV) in soil properties among the different positions on the toposequence. Therefore, the soils were classified as Typic Isohyperthermic Haplustalfs in pedons 2 and 3 with fluvic characters in pedon 1 (USDA) which corresponded to Arenic Luvisols (WRB).

Key words: Toposequence, Landuse, Soil Profile, Soil Classification, Northeast Nigeria

Introduction

The spatial distribution of soil types is related to the topography. The relationships between relief and soil formation processes are manifold (Ojo-Atere et al., 2011). Toposequence and catena concepts have emanated as slope-soil evolutionary processes. However, there is great need to evaluate the toposequence of the soil in order to examine its physical, chemical and biological properties of the soil. Brady and Weil (2014) described toposequence as a sequence of related soil that differ, one from the other, primarily due to topography as a soil forming factor. Soil properties are important to define and evaluate soil types, slope aspects, existing landuse etc. The sustainability and productivity of soil depends on its changing equilibrium in the physical, chemical and biological properties. These properties are spontaneously affected by landuse with profound influence on soil properties and thereby enhancing the restoration of soil quality (Deekor, 2012). Topography as a factor in soil formation is classified as passive factor by Asadu et al. (2011). However, understanding of the impacts of landuse on soil property is indispensable for sustainable agricultural production (Fesha et al., 2002). Spatial variability, parent materials, physiographic position (position of soils on a toposequence) and drainage condition will influence soil fertility and landuse pattern in any given demographic location (Imadojemu, 2021). Soil variation occurs naturally due pedogenic processes, for example soils from summit of a toposequence down to the valley bottom. The movement and transformation of nutrient in soils are influenced by climate and topography (Klemmedson & Weinhold, 1991). Seibert et al. (2007) reported significant correlation between topographic indices and soil properties while Temgoua et al. (2005) concluded that topography is both an internal and external factor in pedogenesis and accounted for about 60% variation in soil properties. The differences in properties of soil occupying different landscape position on a toposequence are caused by water and material movement and distribution along a slope. However, (Moorman, 1981) stated that the different landscape position influence runoff, drainage, erosion and thus dictates soil genesis. The extent of runoff and erosion dictates the surface movement and distribution of basic cation. Soils especially in the tropics are formed in different section of the topography. The rate of soil formation varies along the various segment of the topography such as the crest, middle slope, lower slope and valley bottom as the result of deposition of materials in the various sections of the landform (Osodeke, 2017). Birkeland, (1999) described the soil catena as a chain, string, or a connected series of soils, related by their sequence in the landscape. Therefore, the variability of soils in a topographic sequence is a function of gradient and position on slope and hence a function of time (McFarlane, 1991). Catenary soil sequences occur on hill slopes where the geology is uniform and there is no marked difference in climate from the top to the bottom of the slope. Rather, variations in soil profiles that occur down the slope are largely the result of the changes in slope gradient. Landuse according to Akamigbo (2010) is simply the

activities to which man has put land in order to generate economic output or result while FAO (1984 and 1997) defined land use as the arrangement, activity and input people undertake in a certain land, it involves the cover type to produce it brings, change or maintenance of it. Land that is suitable for agricultural production is finite and vulnerable resource. Senjobi (2001) noted that the practice in developing nation's land use (soil) is often not related to the capacity of the land for that use. Therefore, assessing the spatial variability of soil properties is crucial to sustainable farming practices and reducing the knowledge gap in soil resources management. This study is aimed at determining the properties of soils along the toposequence of Donga River in Manya with a view to classifying the soil for agricultural production

Materials and Method

Study Area

The study was carried out in Manya, Takum Local Government, Taraba State Northeast Nigeria. The area lies between Latitude $7^{\circ} 15' N$ to $7^{\circ} 45' N$ and Longitude $9^{\circ} 59' E$ to $10^{\circ} 25' E$ of the Greenwich meridian. It is largely governed by Inter Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ) defined by two opposing air masses; both the Southwesterlies and the Northeasterlies trade wind (Okusami et al., 1987). It is characterized by hot, sub humid and humid conditions. The area has a tropical hot and wet weather with distinct rainy season (May – October) and dry season (November – April); (Aw Koppen's climate classification); as modified by Peel et al (2007). Annual rainfall ranges from 1218-1480 mm and the rainfall pattern is relatively weak bimodal trend (transitional belt between the rain forest and the southern guinea savanna zones). The mean annual temperature is about $29^{\circ} C$ indicating the tropicity of the environment and characterization of the climate area as hot (temperature can reach $40^{\circ} C$ in March) (Imadojemu, 2021). The temperature of the area, although vary slightly annually and seasonally, remains high throughout the year. Therefore, temperature during the growing season is not a limitation to the adapted crops of the area. In the dry season, minimum and maximum temperatures are generally lower during the harmattan months in most cases, but higher than those for the rainy season during the rest of the season. The relative humidity varies as the rainfall pattern and rate of potential evapotranspiration follows the trend of the relative humidity. The hydrology is governed by Donga River. The major economic activity in the area is farming largely at low to medium scales alongside timber (*Pteracarpuserinaceous*) harvesting.

Vegetation

The area falls within the Agro-ecological zone of woody Savannah vegetation which consists of shrubs, tall grasses (>2 m) and trees especially along the river bank. It also consists of secondary forest regrowth. The area consists of some tree crops such as Oil palm, Mango, Banana, Cocoa and Gmelina arborea while the cultivated crops in the area include Maize (*Zea may*), Cassava (*Manihot spp*), Rice (*oryza sativa*), Fluted pumpkin (*Telifera occidentalis*), Banana (*Musa spp*). Ground nuts (*Arachis hypogeal*), cowpea (*vigna unguiculata*), are produced in large quantities.

Geology and Soil

The geology of the study area is characterized by cretaceous sediments to pre-Cambrian to Cambrian undifferentiated basement complex and such as sand stone materials are the dominant parent materials. The soil found in the study sites are largely the tropical alfisols or luvisols.

Figure 1: Geological Map of Taraba State
Source: Ministry of Lands and Survey, Jalingo, Taraba State.

Figure 1. Geological Map of Taraba State

Field Activities

Reconnaissance survey was carried out in order to obtain general information about the study area. The toposequence were delineated into mapping units based on their physiographic positions (upper slope, mid-slope and valley bottom) along transect spaced at 400 m across the slope. These slope positions also corresponded to different landuse upon which three profile pits were sunk according to the procedures of Soil Survey Staff, (2006). Sampling was based on genetic horizon differentiation. All profile pits were geo-referenced with hand held GPS receiver.

Sample Preparation

The soil samples were air dried at room temperature of 25⁰C for about three days, after which they were sieved using a 2 mm sieve mesh. Some part of the soil samples were passed through 0.5mm mesh sieve for Organic Carbon (O.C) and Total Nitrogen determination.

Laboratory Analysis

Particle size analysis was determined using the Bouyoucos hydrometer method as modified by (Gee and Or, 2002). Bulk density was determined by core method (Grossman and Reinsch, 2002). The moisture content was determined after oven-drying of core soil samples and amount of moisture content was calculated as follows: W_1 =weight of can with lid W_2 =weight of soil+ weight of can with lid, W_3 =weight of oven-dry soil. Total porosity was determined using the formulae

$$\text{Porosity (F)} = 100 - \left(\frac{e_b}{e_s}\right) \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where e_b = bulk density (g/cm^3)

$$e_s = \text{particle density (2.65g/cm}^3\text{)}$$

The soil pH was determined electrometrically using pH meter and this was done in distilled water and 0.1N KCl solution using a soil liquid ratio of 1:2.5 in a glass electrode (Thomas, 1996). Total nitrogen was determined by micro Kjeldahl digestion method (Bremer, 1995). Organic carbon was determined by wet digestion method (Nelson & Sommer, 1982). Available phosphorus was determined using Bray II method as described by (Olsen & Sommer, 1982). Exchangeable acidity was determined by leaching the soil with 1N KCl and titrating with 0.05N NaOH (McClean, 1982). Exchangeable basic cation (Ca^{+2} , Mg^+ , K^+ , Na^+) was determined using 1N NH_4OAc buffered at pH of 7, while K and Na are by flame photometer (Udo, et al., 2009) and Ca and Mg by Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined by ammonium acetate (NH_4OAc) of 1.0M leaching at pH 7 (Blackmore et al., 1987). The available Iron (Fe), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu), and Manganese (Mn) were extracted with DTPA-TEA buffer (0.005M DTPA + 0.01M CaCl_2 + 0.1M TEA at pH 7.3) as described by Verma et al. (2005). The leachate concentration of Zn, Fe, Cu, and Mn were determined using AAS.

Statistical Analysis

Variability amongst selected soil properties was analysed using coefficient of variability coefficient of variation (CV) was ranked according to procedure of Wilding et al., (1994) where $\text{CV} \leq 15\%$ represents low variation, $\text{CV } 15\% \leq \text{CV} \leq 35\%$ (moderate variability) and $> 35\%$ (high variation). The mean values were obtained using weighted mean.

Results and Discussion

The Morphological Properties

The morphological properties of Manya toposequence soils are shown in the table 1. The soil are moderately deep (≥ 100 cm) and porous, the entire horizon were well drained. The soil was loose at all physiographical positions. Pedons 1, 2 and 3 had a fine granular structure in horizon Ap, weak, medium sub-angular structure in horizon AB, angular and sub-angular blocky structure in horizon Bt1 and Bt2 respectively. The profiles on physiographical positions varied in colour matrix. Pedon 1, had dark brown colouration (7.5YR 3/2) in the Ap horizon brown colouration (7.5YR 5/3) in the AB horizon, with brown colouration (7.5YR 5/2) with a lighter chroma in the Bt1 horizon and light grey colour (5YR 7/1) in the Bt2. Pedon 2 recorded a reddish brown (2.5YR 4/3) in its Ap horizon while brown colour (7.5YR 4/4) was observed in the AB horizon whereas a dark reddish brown (2.5YR 3/3) and a brown (10YR4/3) were observed in Bt1 and Bt2 horizons respectfully. Pedon 3 had dark reddish brown (2.5YR 2.5/4), strong brown (7.5YR 5/8), pink (7.5YR 7/3) and pinkish white (7.5YR 8/2) in its genetic horizons of Ap, AB, Bt1 and Bt2 respectively. The colour matrix and other morphological characteristics of the soil suggest that the soils are under the same pedogenic processes. The colour matrix of dark yellowish brown, strong brown and reddish yellow are associated with minerals such as Goethite (FeOOH) and Haematite (Fe_2O_3). The sub angular and angular structures found in the Bt horizons are indicative of illuviation processes (Imadojemu, 2021).

The Physical Properties

The physical properties on the studied pedons are presented in table 2. It was observed generally that the contents of sand and silt fractions dominated the soil peds. The higher content of silt over clay indicates that the soil has reserved weatherable mineral. This has a positive implication for soil fertility status as about 50% of the textural class in the study area were silty loam while about 43% were sandy loam. The preponderance of loamic texture connotes higher nutrient retention. Mean sand content were 43.00 g/kg⁻¹, 71.47 g/kg⁻¹ and 39.64 for Pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The highest values of silt were observed at the Bt2 horizons at 558 g/kg⁻¹, 366 g/kg⁻¹ and 680 g/kg⁻¹ for Pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The proportion of clay decreased with increase in profile depth. The SCR mean for Pedons 1, 2 and 3 were 38.61, 93.11 and 67.55 respectively. Yakubu and Ojanuga, (2009) reported that SCR below 0.15 was indicative of an old soils (senile) while SCR above 0.15 was indicative of a young soil with weatherable reserves. Bulk density (in g/cm³) tends to be higher in the top soils; this may be due to anthropogenic activities. The mean bulk densities were

Table 1: Morphological Properties of the studied soils

CO-ORDINAT ES	HORIZON	DEPTH (cm)	COLOUR (moist)	STRUCTURE	MOTTLE	HORIZON BOUNDARY	TEXTURE	CONSIST.	VEG	ROOT PRES.
Rice Landuse (Pedon 1) (Valley bottom)										
7° 19' 15" N 10° 14' 45" E	Ap	0-14	Dark brown 7.5YR3/2	Granular	Few	Clear, smooth	Fine	Friable	SR	Many
	AB	14-40	Brown 7.5YR5/3	Sub-angular	Very few	Diffuse, wavy	Fine	Firm	SR	Few
	Bt1	40-70	Brown 7.5YR5/2	Angular Sub-angular	Many	Clear, smooth	Fine	Very firm	SR	Very few
	Bt2	70-100	Light grey 5YR7/1	block	Many	Clear, smooth	Fine	Firm	SR	Absence
Cassava Landuse (Pedon 2) (Mild slope)										
7° 19' 16.2" N 7° 19' 46.5" E	Ap	0-13	Reddish brown 2.5YR4/3	Granular	Very few	Clear, wavy	Coarse	Friable	SR	Many
	AB	13-50	Brown 7.5YR4/3	Sub-angular Sub-angular	Common	Clear, wavy	Coarse	Firm	SR	Few
	Bt1	50-70	Dark reddish brown 2.5YR3/3	block	Common	Common	Very fine	Firm	SR	Very few
	Bt2	70-100	Brown 10YR4/3	Angular	Common	Common	Fine	Firm	SR	Very few
Mixed Crop Landuse (Pedon 3) Summit slope										
7° 19' 14.2" N 10° 14' 43.3" NE	Ap	0-20	Dark reddish brown 2.5YR2.5/4	Granular	Many	Clear, smooth	Coarse	Friable	SR	Many
	AB	20-56	Strong brown 7.5YR5/8	Sub-angular	Few	Clear, smooth	Coarse	Firm	SR	Few
	Bt1	56-80	Pink 7.5YR7/3	Blocky	Few	Clear, smooth	Fine	Hard	SR	Few
	Bt2	80-110	Pinkish brown 7.5YR8/2	Angular	Common	Clear, smooth	Fine	Hard	SR	Few

All colour were taken under moist condition, SR: Secondary Regrowth, Consist: Soil consistency

1.24 g/cm³, 1.39 g/cm³ and 1.57 g/cm³ for pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The values obtained for bulk density agrees with those earlier reported by Imadojemu *et al* (2017) and Obasi *et al* (2021) while Esu (2010) reported that bulk density value less than 1.60 g/cm³ is an indication that air and water movement in the soil are at optimum. The mean values for porosity showed that the soil root zone had no impediments to gaseous exchange. Porosity normally have inverse relationship with bulk density and both have profound effect on infiltration, rooting depth, soil aeration, available plant water and soil microbial functions.

Table 2. *Physical Properties of the Studied Soils*

Horizon Designation	Depth (cm)	SAND g/kg ⁻¹	SILT g/kg ⁻¹	CLAY g/kg ⁻¹	SCR	TC	BD (g/cm ⁻³)	Po (%)	MC (%)
RICE LANDUSE (Pedon 1)									
Ap	0-14	514	432	54	8	Sandy loam	1.16	56.6	8.5
AB	14-40	332	646	22	29.36	Silt loam	1.36	48.7	11.59
Bt1	40-70	472	516	12	43	Silt loam	1.26	52.65	13.7
Bt2	70-100	434	558	10	55.8	Silt loam	1.19	55.09	13.95
Mean		430	550	19	38.61		1.24	53.26	12.5
CV		143	110	105.85	52.8		15	47.53	20.85
CASSAVA LANDUSE (Pedon 2)									
Ap	0-13	71.12	24.2	4.6	5.26	Sandy loam	1.67	36.98	25.55
AB	13-50	75.2	24.2	0.6	40.33	Sandy loam	1.19	55.09	25.13
Bt1	50-70	77.2	22.6	0.2	113	Loamy sand	1.39	47.54	25.91
Bt2	70-100	63.2	36.6	0.2	183	Sandy loam	1.32	50.2	11.97
Mean		71.47	27.6	0.92	93.11		1.39	47.45	21.39
CV		8.67	23.77	240.46	85.43		11.44	50.51	31.98
MIXED CROP (Pedon 3)									
Ap	0-20	51.2	48.2	0.6	80.33	Sandy loam	1.43	46.04	12.21
AB	20-56	43.2	56	0.8	70	Silt loam	1.53	42.3	25.16
Bt1	56-80	35.2	62.8	2	31.4	Silt loam	1.66	37.36	15.34
Bt2	80-110	31.2	68	0.8	85	Silt loam	1.67	36.98	13.33
Mean		39.64	59.34	1.02	67.55		1.57	40.67	17.44
CV		22.44	1450	6250	36.07		10.33	25.86	34.45

SCR: silt clay ratio, Po: porosity (%), MC: moisture content (%), TC: Textural Class

The Chemical Properties

The chemical properties of the soils are shown in table 3. The soil pH (water) had mean values of 6.48, 5.80, and 5.95 in Pedons 1, 2, and 3 respectively. Pedon 1 had the mean with the least acidity mean value (6.48), while Pedon 2 had the highest mean with value (5.80). The acidity increased down the profile, the soil pH in water ranged from moderately to slightly acid which is ideal for most crop production according to the rating of Chude et al., (2011).

Table 3: Chemical Properties of the Studied Soils

Depth (cm)	pH H ₂ O	pH KCl	ΔPH	OC	TN	C/N Ratio	Av.P (Mg/Kg)	Ca	Mg	K	Na	cmol/Kg				Ca/Mg Ratio	%BS	(mg/Kg)			
							ECEC					TEB	TEA	Zn	Fe			Cu	Mn		
Rice landuse (Pedon 1)																					
0-14	7.05	4.25	-2.8	1.95	0.85	2.29	96.75	4.5	0.81	1.41	2.17	9.04	8.89	0.15	5.56	98.34	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.08	
14-40	6.75	4.05	-2.7	0.59	0.75	0.79	92.24	4.61	0.81	1.66	2.21	9.64	9.29	0.35	5.69	96.37	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.27	
40-70	6.6	3.95	-2.65	0.62	0.95	0.65	122.21	4.5	0.82	1.99	2.18	9.74	9.49	0.25	5.49	97.43	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.18	
70-100	5.85	4.05	-1.8	0.47	0.65	0.72	98.94	4.5	0.81	1.53	2.04	9.23	8.88	0.35	5.56	96.21	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.27	
mean	6.48	4.05	-2.43	0.75	0.79	23.43	103.87	4.53	0.81	1.69	2.14	9.46	9.17	0.29	5.57	96.92	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.21	
CV	4.78	-33.4	40.84	40.84	2.41	28.8	10.6	18.71	18.65	6.41	42.6	17.14	6.3	18.65	0.88	16.33	25.85	25.87	14.93	25.87	
Cassava Landuse (Pedon 2)																					
0-13	5.95	4.25	-1.7	1.15	0.95	2.1	97.04	4.6	0.81	1.92	2.27	9.75	9.6	0.15	5.68	98.46	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.08	
13-50	5.85	4.05	-1.8	0.68	0.75	0.91	89.13	4.5	0.82	2.34	2.31	10.32	9.97	0.35	5.49	96.61	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.28	
50-70	5.75	4	-1.75	0.3	0.85	0.35	67.14	4.6	0.81	2.37	2.27	10.25	10.05	0.2	5.68	98.05	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.12	
70-100	5.7	3.95	-1.75	0.95	0.95	1.00	54.61	4.6	0.81	1.97	2.42	10.15	9.8	0.35	5.68	96.55	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.27	
Mean	5.8	4.04	-1.76	0.75	0.86	24.49	75.4	4.56	0.81	2.18	2.33	10.18	9.89	0.29	5.61	97.12	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.22	
CV	12.49	36.46	55.44	55.44	1.11	23.63	10.67	53.19	34.81	32.57	37.88	53.33	62.89	31.02	34.42	70.59	21.19	24.97	23.16	32.78	
Mixed Crop Landuse (Pedon 3)																					
0-20	5.7	4.05	-1.65	0.12	0.25	0.48	14.27	4.6	0.82	1.67	2.37	10.03	9.48	0.55	5.61	94.52	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.48	
20-56	5.65	3.85	-1.8	0.74	0.2	3.7	12.22	4.5	0.82	1.58	2.46	9.86	9.36	0.5	5.49	94.93	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.43	
56-80	5.65	3.9	-1.75	0.65	0.15	4.33	12.19	4.9	0.81	1.63	2.46	10.2	9.8	0.4	6.05	96.08	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.33	
80-110	6.7	3.85	-2.85	0.62	0.1	6.2	11.76	4.72	0.81	1.59	2.37	9.74	9.49	0.25	5.83	97.43	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.17	
Mean	5.95	3.9	-2.05	0.58	0.17	26.04	12.46	4.67	0.82	1.61	2.42	9.93	9.51	0.42	5.73	95.79	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.35	
CV	12.69	9.05	40.03	34.62	36.44	1.85	25.87	4.08	24.2	14.29	13.93	54.9	26.85	18.37	32.04	1.04	17.83	29.06	25.28	10.96	

C/N: Carbon Nitrogen ratio, OC: Organic Carbon, TN: Total Nitrogen, ECEC: Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, TEB: Total Exchangeable Bases, TEA: Total Exchangeable Acidity, AvP: Available Phosphorus

The pH in KCl had mean values of 4.05, 4.04 and 3.90 in Pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. The negative ΔpH values obtained are indicative that the colloidal fraction has exchangeable capacity- cation exchangers (Imadojemu, 2021). The mean of the total Nitrogen (TN) had a value of 0.79%, 0.86% and 0.17% in Pedon 1, 2, and 3 respectively. Highest mean (0.86%) was observed in Pedon 2, while the lowest mean had a value of (0.17%) recorded in Pedon 3. The percentage of nitrogen was rated very low based on soil fertility classes for Nigerian soils (Onyilola and Chude, 2010; Chude et al., 2011). The low values obtained in pedon 3 (summit slope) may be due to its physiographic position. The C:N is important for determining mineralization and immobilization of nitrogen, C:N of ≤ 25 is reported to favour mineralization of organic matter by soil microbes. The Available phosphorus had a mean of 103.87 mg/kg, 75.40 mg/kg and 12.46 mg/kg in Pedon 1, 2, and 3 respectively. The highest mean (103.87 mg/kg) was recorded in Pedon 1. The available phosphorus in the soil was rated very high. For Calcium, an estimated mean of 4.53 cmol/kg, 4.56 cmol/kg and 4.67 cmol/kg in Pedon 1, 2 and 3 respectively. Sodium (Na) had a mean range of 2.14 cmol/kg, 2.33 cmol/kg and 2.42 cmol/kg in Pedon 1, 2, and 3 respectively. The ECEC was dominated by Ca and Na. However, high content of Na did not constitute any threat to crop production. The ECEC had mean value ≥ 9 cmol/kg which is rated high and also evidence of 2:1 clay minerals (Ukaegbu et al., 2015). Percentage Base Saturation had a mean that ranged from 96.72%, 97.12% and 95.79% in pedons 1, 2 and 3 respectively. These high percentage base saturations are suggestive of Alfisols-Entisols mix. The mean for the proportion of manganese in the Pedon had values 0.21 %, 0.22% and 0.35 % in Pedon 1, 2, and 3 respectively. The mean values obtained for Mn, Cu, Fe and Zn were relatively low and does not pose any deleterious effect to agriculture landuse. This low level of micronutrient was also reported by Zaku et al. (2011).

Taxonomic Classification

The soils of the study area were classified using USDA Soil Taxonomy system (2015), and correlated with World Reference Base (2006). In classifying these soils, certain criteria were considered. This include the nature of the epipedon, the types of diagnostic master horizon, the clay content, the organic matter content, the percentage base saturation, the presence or absence of concretions (plinthitic features), the soil moisture, temperature regimes and soils colour. The soils tends to have more bright hues (reddish brown) due to good aeration, these pedons was classified as in the order as Alfisols/ Entisols mix because of the presence of Bt horizon and the absence of lamellae, suborder as utsalfs owing to the ustic moisture regime, great group as Argillic Haplaqualfs as the most horizons are argillic along with high OC contents as well as the high %BS while the preponderance of sand showed psammentic (USDA) correlates to Arenic (WRB). The subgroup was classified Eutric Siltic Haplustalfs. The family was classified coarse Silty Loam, Superactive Isohyperthermic, ustalfs. Series was Manya Silty Loam. This corresponds to Arenic Luvisols (pedons 2 and 3) with fluvic characteristics in pedon 1 (WRB, 2006).

Conclusion

The results of the morphological, physical and chemical properties of the soil showed variability in profile depths and physiographic positions. The profiles were moderately deep, well drained and silt fraction dominated other fractions of the soil. The presence of Bt horizons of silt loam texture indicated that the soil had reserved weatherable minerals. The bulk density and porosity of the soil were within range for good crop cultivation. Soil pH was moderately acid to slightly acid, organic matter was generally low in all the pedons. Available phosphorus ranged from very high to high. Therefore, the soils were classified as Typic Isohyperthermic Haplustalfs in pedons 2 and 3 with fluvic characters in pedon 1 (USDA) and Arenic Luvisols (WRB)

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